

EPOS SP – Grant Agreement n. 871121

D1.1 - Management and Quality Control Plan

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1.3	18 March 2020	Initial version (EPOS ERIC ECO)
2	25 March 2020	Impact Assessment chapter has been updated according to procedures agreed during the EB telco held on 23 March 2020. (EB – ECO)
3	30 March 2020	WP2 Leader's comments included in chapter 1, 2, 4; WP3 Leader's comments included in paragraph 3.4.

Table of content

Executive summary.....	3
1. Introduction.....	4
2. EPOS SP Management Structure	4
2.1 Project Council	5
2.2 Executive Board	5
2.3 National Authorities Consultation Board	5
2.4 Advisory Board.....	6
3. Quality Control Procedures	7
3.1 Submission of Deliverables	7
3.2 Quality of Deliverables	8
3.3 Submission of EC Periodic and Final Reports	9
3.4 Quality of EC Periodic and Final Reports.....	9
4. Impact Assessment	11
5. Risks Management.....	13
6. Internal Communication	14
7. Conclusion	15
Annex 1 - Deliverable Template	16
Annex 2 - Reporting Templates.....	17

Executive summary

The EPOS SP project is aimed at ensuring the long-term sustainability of the EPOS Research Infrastructure (RI). It is perfectly placed in the EPOS RI lifecycle since it will consolidate the EPOS ERIC and the EPOS Delivery Framework operations into a very long-term perspective of operations.

The project is one of the specific objectives listed in the EPOS ERIC Strategic Plan 2020 – 2022 where it is highlighted that the EPOS SP represents the collaborative framework in which addressing the challenges of financial viability and long-term sustainability together with the EPOS community. Therefore, the project represents an essential contribution to the EPOS ERIC planning for the next three years, because it contributes in keeping the communities committed to support the building of the EPOS Delivery Framework dealing with both the holistic concept of sustainability and effective practices to achieve this ambitious goal. Thus, all the activities and processes foreseen in the EPOS SP project, including the management of the project, will be guided and carried out considering this framework.

This Deliverable describes the structure and the procedures adopted to guarantee the effective management of the EPOS SP project. It provides guidelines on management and quality control procedures of the project to ensure that a standard quality level is kept in different activities (management related issues, preparation and submission of deliverables, reporting procedures, KPIs, internal communication).

Therefore, this deliverable should be considered the guide for EPOS SP beneficiaries for all aspects of the project's organisational structures, quality control process, reporting schedule and contractual obligations.

1. Introduction

The Project Management (WP1) is responsible to guarantee an effective, smooth and high-quality performance of the EPOS SP project considering that the project outcomes will be presented to the EPOS ERIC General Assembly for their evaluation and adoption.

This Deliverable presents the management and quality control plan of the EPOS SP project. It describes procedures adopted for guaranteeing a consistent quality of the EPOS SP outcomes. In particular, the following issues are considered:

- composition, role, decision making process and responsibility of the EPOS SP management and governing bodies;
- identification of the quality control procedures that are needed for ensuring an effective, smooth and high-quality management of the project;
- monitoring of the workflow and performances through suitable indicators;
- adoption of suitable tools for ensuring an effective internal communication.

2. EPOS SP Management Structure

The management structure of the EPOS SP projects has been designed to guarantee the appropriate level of quality of the contractual, ethical, financial and administrative organisation of the project. It is described in the Grant Agreement (WP1 and section 3.2) and formalised in the Consortium Agreement. Each project Beneficiary has specific roles and in general, it should fulfil its tasks duly, timely and according to the distribution of work specified in the Description of Action (DoA).

The following project' roles are defined:

The **Project Coordinator** has the overall responsibility of the organization, planning and control of the EPOS SP project. She acts as the intermediary for all communications between the beneficiaries and the European Commission. The Project Coordinator is supported by the Executive Coordination Office (ECO) of EPOS ERIC. The ECO will assist the Project Coordinator in managing the project and it will ensure interactions and communication between EPOS SP and EPOS ERIC.

The **Work Package Leader** is responsible for coordinating the work done by all beneficiaries involved in the work package (WP). The WP Leader presents the work package progress to the Executive Board and Project Council. WP Leader reviews all deliverables in the WP and is responsible of their quality check and on time delivery to the Coordinator, in order to guarantee the submission to the European Commission in accordance with the Grant Agreement.

The **Task Leader** is responsible for coordinating and reporting the work done by all beneficiaries involved in the task. The Task Leader presents the task progress when required by the WP Leader and interacts with the Project Management Office for contributing to the management process.

The Governance of the EPOS SP project is made up of a governing body, the **Project Council (PC)**, an executive body, the **Executive Board (EB)**, a consultation board, the **National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB)** and an advisory body, the **Advisory Board (AB)**.

2.1 Project Council

The Project Council (PC) is the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium. The Project Council consists of one representative of each Consortium Beneficiary and it is chaired by the Project Coordinator. It meets at least once a year. The first PC meeting took place during the EPOS SP kick-off meeting, held in Brussels on the 10-12 February 2020. During the meeting it was decided to have the second PC meeting on February 2021 and the third meeting on February 2022. Extraordinary meetings will be held at any time upon request of the Executive Board or of one third of the Members of the PC.

The PC supervises the project work plan on a high level and is the only body with authority to alter the work plan to any significant degree. Main decisions taken by the PC are related to content, finances and intellectual property rights as well as to evolution of the consortium¹. Decisions shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds of the votes cast. A decision is being escalated at PC level (in either the administrative, financial, scientific or technical domain) whenever the decision impacts the Project objectives or when the Executive Board cannot reach a consensus.

2.2 Executive Board

The Executive Board (EB) is composed by the work package Leaders and by the Project Coordinator. The EB monitors and controls the project activities and budget and it will ensure implementation of the Grant Agreement signed with the European Commission. The EB meetings will be held regularly. The first EB meeting took place during the EPOS SP kick-off meeting (Brussels-10-12 February 2020). During the meeting the schedule of the meetings foreseen for the entire duration of the project was presented. In particular for the 2020 the following schedule have been agreed for face to face and telco:

- **March 2020 (M2):** telco for KPIs and Risk Register approval and Advisory Board composition discussion;
- **July 2020 (M5):** face to face meeting for monitoring project activities, and interaction with WP8;
- **October 2020 (M9):** telco for updating on the project activities;
- **December 2020 (M11):** face to face meeting for assessing the first interim report.

The EB is also responsible to empower the Project Coordinator to inform PC about any significant deviations in the project activities and is responsible to provide solutions and proposals as a part of the risk management². Decisions of the EB shall be taken by a majority of two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast.

2.3 National Authorities Consultation Board

The **National Authorities Consultation Board (NACB)** is made up of Governmental Representatives from those countries not yet engaged in EPOS or engaged in EPOS, but that did not join yet EPOS ERIC. The NACB is not a decision body in EPOS SP. It is a consultation board in which national authorities can follow the EPOS progress to increase their interest in EPOS and find information and documents necessary to start the national process to join EPOS ERIC. The following countries already expressed their interest to be involved in this board: Austria, Romania, Slovak Republic, Spain, Germany and Sweden. Others are expected to participate, such as: Czech Republic, Finland, Ireland, Turkey, and Hungary. The communication and cooperation activities undertaken in EPOS SP (in WP2, WP4, WP7) are dedicated to engage in the NACB new countries such as Bulgaria, Serbia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Albania, Republic of North Macedonia, among several others. The establishment process of NACB will be managed by EPOS ERIC and their engagement is expected by July 2020.

¹ Art. 6.3.1.2 of the EPOS SP Consortium Agreement.

² Art. 6.3.2.3.6 of the EPOS SP Consortium Agreement.

2.4 Advisory Board

External **Advisory Board (AB)** is composed of experts, not engaged in EPOS, such as research infrastructures managers, international outstanding scientists, e-science international experts, managers from the private sector. The AB has the goal to supplement EPOS SP consortium expertise and to provide advices throughout different stages of the EPOS SP development and implementation. Advisory Board members will be proposed by the EB and approved by the PC. The AB will be appointed by May 2020.³

³ Art. 6.7 of the EPOS SP Consortium Agreement.

3. Quality Control Procedures

The definition of quality control procedures is necessary to guarantee high-quality project outputs, including the degree of fulfilment of EPOS SP objectives and the status of each work package activity for the analysed period, in order to ensure the best quality in preparation of the deliverables, interim, periodic and final reports.

The purposes of the quality control procedures are the following:

- make the EPOS SP stakeholders confident in the quality of the work that the project teams are performing, putting in evidence how the project is developed, measured, monitored, accounted and safeguarded during its implementation,
- clearly define the content, format, sign-off and review process, and responsibilities for each deliverable,
- provide the Executive Board (EB), acting as executive body, with adequate information to organize quality assurance and control activities that include transfer of information, verification actions, etc.,
- provide all the project participants with procedures, rules and applicable methods.

The Project Coordinator will supervise and guarantee a consistent quality of the EPOS SP outcomes. She will be supported by the Executive Board (EB) for dealing both strategic and technical issues and will be responsible for the timely delivery of results on behalf of each partner, assuring the quality of the work executed, monitoring budgetary and technical results.

3.1 Submission of Deliverables

Deliverables are official documents, accompanying periodic reports, which are included in EPOS SP Grant Agreement (GA) - DoA. They are used to provide information on project developments and results to the EC and to project's stakeholders but also to hand over definitions, results to other work packages and tasks in the project. Therefore, quality assurance process focuses on ensuring high quality of deliverables and conformity with the Grant Agreement.

In the DoA each deliverable is identified by the Lead Beneficiary, responsible for its production. The Lead Beneficiary is requested to maintain adequate control on the participants' contributions. This duty is extended to all levels of third parties.

The Lead Beneficiary's responsibilities include the following activities:

- assembling and homogenizing inputs from task/WP partners;
- document writing and editing;
- document finalization and revision by the WP leader;
- document submission to the Coordinator and to the Executive Board for final approval, in good time for submission to the EC.

Deliverables will be submitted in accordance with the timetable specified in the DoA deliverable's list. Formal responsibility for submitting deliverables to the European Commission is taken by the Coordinator.

Deliverable documents are edited following a standard format (see: Annex 1 - Deliverable Template) created within the scope of the project and circulated to the partners and stored in the EPOS SP Intranet Area. The use of the format-template for deliverables is *mandatory*.

3.2 Quality of Deliverables

The deliverable review process ensures the high quality of the project deliverables, which should meet the expectations of project objectives and results as defined in the Grant Agreement. It also improves the quality of the project outputs and it minimizes the risks of rejections.

Table 1 shows the six steps of the Deliverable review process along with a time estimation for each step.

While elaborating the draft version of the deliverable, the Lead-beneficiary Contact Person should take into account the following checklist and use the best endeavours to ensure that the deliverable:

- addresses clearly and in sufficient depth the subject matter and the objectives described in the DoA (any deviation, if present, must be sufficiently motivated and explained);
- is factually correct, tailored for the size and complexity of the Task, putting the work in relation with the EPOS SP architecture and goals;
- quotes and discusses sufficiently the related work;
- mentions in explicit way the items referred to other/later deliverables, (e.g. the complete deliverable numbering ref.) and includes a glossary of acronyms and main terms (in particular for Public deliverables);
- is spell-checked and conforms to the standard deliverable format (see Annex 1: Deliverables Template).

Table 1. Deliverables review process

Step	Who	What	When
1	Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person	The Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person shares the draft version of the deliverable with the Task Leaders and/or WP Participants (WP Team) to ensure the completeness of the work and results achieved. [If relevant]	During the elaboration process.
2	WP Leader	The WP Leader assesses the deliverable to ensure the quality standard and timely delivery. This assessment might request modifications or the rejection of the deliverable that do not adequately fulfil the quality standard criteria; the Lead-Beneficiary should use the best endeavours to avoid any possible disagreement.	As soon the WP Leader has received the document from the Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person (15/20 days before the deadline set in the DoA).
3	Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person	The Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person sends the (revised) draft of the deliverable to the Management Office (management@epos-eric.eu) to be forwarded to the Executive Board for comments.	At least 10 days before the deadline set in the DoA.
4	Executive Board	It provides comments to the Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person. Tacit Consent rule applies.	Within one week from the day the deliverable is sent.
5	Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person	The Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person acknowledges comments (if any) and send the revised deliverable to the Management Office (management@epos-eric.eu).	Within two days from the day comments are sent.
6	Coordinator	The Coordinator submits the final Deliverable to the European Commission. The final Deliverable is stored in the intranet shared area.	In respect of the DoA deadline.

The Lead-Beneficiary Contact Person should inform and motivate the WP Leader concerned and the Executive Board in case the deliverable is delayed or not made available at the deadline specified. The same applies by the WP leader/s in case of the reviewer feedback is ongoing beyond the deadline limit.

3.3 Submission of EC Periodic and Final Reports

The project periodic and final reports, which have to be submitted to the EC by the Coordinator, require a high level of accuracy of data, quality of partners contributions and the commitment to strict deadlines.

According to art. 20.2 MGA, EPOS SP project is divided into two reporting periods:

- RP1: from month 1 to month 18 (*from February 2020 to July 2021*)
- RP2: from month 19 to month 36 (*from September 2021 to January 2023*)

The Coordinator must submit a **Periodic Report** – including both technical and financial report - within **60 days** following the end of each reporting period.

In addition to the Periodic Report for the last reporting period, the coordinator must submit a **Final Report**, including a final technical report and the certificates on financial statements (if applicable, depending on the overall EC contribution claimed⁴).

The prompt and accurate submission of periodic and final reports directly affects the distribution of interim and final payments by the EC.

In view of favouring a smooth and straightforward process, the Executive Coordination Office (ECO) has elaborated specific internal procedures and templates for technical and financial reporting.

Internal reporting procedures foresee, in addition to the Periodic reports, an interim report exercise, to be carried out halfway during each reporting period – **specifically at M9 (October 2020), M27 (April 2022)** – which will pave the way to the official reporting to the EC. Furthermore, interim reports will help monitoring the beneficiaries'/linked third parties' cash flow. Being informal, the interim report won't be submitted to the EC and will be shared only internally.

Reporting templates are edited following a standard format (see: Annex 2 - Reporting Template). They reflect the level of information required by the EC for EPOS SP Periodic and Final reports, and aim at supporting partners both from technical and financial point of view. The templates will be circulated to the partners and stored in the EPOS SP Intranet Area. The use of the format-template for reporting is *mandatory*.

3.4 Quality of EC Periodic and Final Reports

Reports must be completed by the Coordinator assisted by the WP leaders using the information supplied by partners. The Coordinator, collates and reviews the financial and technical reports, compiles them into the summary documents and consolidate the document.

The completion and the quality check of **WP Technical reports** is under the WP Leaders' responsibility.

To this end, each WP Leader will:

- address clearly and in sufficient depth the work carried out during the reporting period in line with the DoA (any deviation, if present, must be sufficiently motivated and explained);
- assure that the report is concise and readable;

⁴ Such a certificate is needed if the beneficiary/linked third party⁴ requests a total financial contribution of EUR 325.000 (or more) as reimbursement for actual costs and personnel costs declared on the basis of unit costs calculated according to its usual accounting practices.

- control that it is spell-checked and conforms to the standard report format (see Annex 2: Technical Report Template);
- assemble contributions and homogenizing inputs from WP partners and transmits the WP Technical Report to the ECO **within 30 days** from the end of the reporting period or accordingly with the ECO schedule.

It is foreseen that all draft versions of Technical Report are circulated by the WP Leader to the Task Leaders to ensure the completeness of the work carried out at task and WP level.

Each Beneficiary (and, if applicable, its linked third parties) is responsible to fill in its own **financial reporting** and list of dissemination and communication activities. Each Beneficiary is requested to send complete financial report, for assessment the coherence with the GA-Annex II, to the ECO **within 30 days** from the end of the reporting period or accordingly with the ECO schedule.

The Coordinator is requested to proceed with the on-line submission of the whole Periodic Report when the set of reports is complete.

In case of partner/s which do not complete on time their Form C on the EC Single Electronic Data Interchange Area (SEDIA) – and to avoid delays with the EC interim payments, affecting all other partners - the Coordinator, supported by the EB, may decide that no Financial Statements for their organisations will be included in the submission to the EC for that reporting period. Consequently, the partner/s will not receive any interim payment for that reporting period.

The individual financial statements not submitted for a reporting period, it may be included in the periodic financial report for the next reporting period.

4. Impact Assessment

EPOS SP project is committed to preserve and build on the successful achievements of the EPOS Implementation Phase, while developing a sustainability plan to be endorsed and adopted by EPOS ERIC for the entire Delivery Framework. Therefore, actions and activities have been planned to ensure the project will have an impact on: Value for Users; Scientific Value; Community Building; Economic Value; Societal Value.

Each of these impacts will be ensured following specific approaches in the EPOS SP work program:

- **Value for Users:** enhancing sustainability of the data and service provision that includes reinforcing and preserving the trust and awareness of users.
- **Scientific Value:** sustaining the use of the EPOS pan-European infrastructure to ensure progress and innovation in science responding to society and industry needs.
- **Community Building:** fostering participation to the EPOS integration plan and awareness of data sharing, also enhancing the role of the EPOS Community in European and international organizations/initiatives and multilateral fora.
- **Economic Value:** fostering the integration of research and innovation in solid Earth science also by establishing a sustainable framework for cooperating with the private sector, including industry and SMEs.
- **Societal Value:** increasing the added value to society derived from sharing data, products and information concerning both EPOS hazard and risk and EPOS readiness for Open Science, clarifying the ethical dimension of the EPOS service provision to society.

The impact of the project in the framework of the entire EPOS Delivery Framework will be then assessed through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and qualitative impact indicators as reported in the DoA.

Moreover, specific KPIs, focused on the objectives of each work package, in particular, have been identified and will be used as tools to:

- measure how effectively the project is achieving key objectives listed in the DoA;
- early warning about related risks (risks as mapped in the Risks Register);
- contribute to the project impact assessment.

The list of those specific KPIs has been elaborated by each WP Leader for the concerned WP, shared within the EB and approved by the Board. The definition of KPIs has been focused and tailor-made to measure the performance, effectiveness and relevance of the activities executed in the different Work Packages (WPs), and they were tested against the RACER criteria⁵.

They had to be:

- **Relevant** – i.e. closely linked to the objectives to be achieved
- **Accepted** – e.g. by staff and stakeholders
- **Credible** for non-experts, unambiguous and easy to interpret
- **Easy to monitor** – e.g. data collection should be possible at low cost
- **Robust** – e.g. against manipulation

Each WP Leader is responsible for updating the proposed KPIs, their objectives, purpose and measure tools. Indeed, a monitoring process, at M9 and M27, is foreseen to periodically evaluate and update KPIs to meet

⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/competition/publications/reports/kd0117397enn.pdf>

the project's goals. Corrective actions (if relevant) will be proposed by the respective WP leader to the EB for their evaluation and application. Only those corrective actions considered relevant for ensuring: i) the expected impacts of the project and ii) the proper management of the risks, will be considered valid and applicable.

The EB will, therefore, consider the global impact of these measures and assess the possible risks, together with the relevant corrective measures.

A detailed classification and evaluation will be provided within the following Deliverables: D1.4 "First report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards" at M12 and D1.5 "Final report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards" at M30.

5. Risks Management

To guarantee the achievement of the objectives of the EPOS SP project, it is essential to identify and understand the significant project risks. The continuous risk management process is based on the early identification of, and the fast reaction to, events that can negatively affect the outcome of the project. The identified risks are then analysed and graded, based on impact and probability of occurrence.

The EPOS SP risk management plan has been defined to ensure that the project progresses smoothly towards the successful achievement of the planned results following its roadmap to reach the envisaged long-term sustainability. This process aims at identifying, analysing and prioritizing risks inherent in the project and then determining the appropriate actions to eliminate or mitigate their effects.

Following the successfully risks management implemented during the EPOS Implementation Phase, the same approach has been used for the EPOS SP project. It consists of a three-level system:

- the **EPOS Risk Management Policy** that sets out the principles, outlines the priorities, assigns responsibility and instructs the project Executive Board to put in place and to follow;
- the **EPOS SP Risk Management Plan** that covers the processes and activities to be undertaken in order to give effect to the Risk Management Policy;
- the dynamic **EPOS SP Risk Register** that comprises a frequently updated database listing all the identified risks, a current assessment of the threat(s) they represent to the success of EPOS SP, the entities responsible for taking appropriate action, the potential action, and its current status.

WP Leaders will define the risks may occur at WP level taking into account the critical risks for implementation Table 3.2b of the DoA. The Risk Register, that will include all risks defined, will be approved by the Executive Board (EB). It is considered a live document and it will be monitored on a regular basis (M9, M18, M27, M36) by the WP Leaders. An updated risk table will be provided if new unforeseen/seeable risks will be identified. The WP Leader is responsible to inform the ECO of its decisions and measures taken to mitigate these risks at WP level.

The Risk Management Policy and Plan as well as the first release of the Risk Register represent a WP1 deliverable (D1.2) due at April 2020. Further, a detailed classification and evaluation will be provided within the following Deliverables: D1.4 “First report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards” at M12 and D1.5 “Final report on KPIs and risks monitoring to internal boards” at M30.

6. Internal Communication

The internal communications will be carried out within the members of the consortium. Internal communication aims at ensuring a proper project execution optimizing the flow of general communication between partners according to the management structure. The establishment of an efficient internal communication is essential to ensure awareness of the EPOS SP mission, share efforts to foster achievements, maintain workflow and timeline, share responsibilities for risk management.

The main tools that will be used during the project to accomplish the internal communication among the partners are:

1. the **EPOS SP intranet area** is designed taking into account the management structure of the project. A number of features will be included such as: work spaces, file sharing/repository, mailing lists, event management tool, web conference tool, project task management tool, calendar, etc. Further details on the Intranet will be available by April 2020 when it will be made available for all partners.
2. **regular meetings face-to-face and/or teleconferences** organised for the different EPOS SP Boards for ensuring the proper interaction between parties of the same Work Package (WP) as well as between parties of different WPs to exchange main results gained and to monitor performance, effectiveness and relevance of the activities executed. This is extremely important for the EPOS SP project because of the important interconnections among WPs.

The following face to face meetings have been already planned for the entire project lifetime:

- three Project Council (PC) with the participation of all EPOS SP beneficiaries (one per year);
- seven Executive Board (EB) with the participation of WP Leaders (two per year approximately);
- three National Authorities Consulting Board (NACB) with the participation of representatives of countries not yet member of EPOS ERIC to cultivate the interest of the National Authorities and scientific communities in EPOS (one per year);
- three Advisory Board (AB) with the participation of Advisory Board members (one per year).

Additional face-to-face meetings or teleconferences might be organised if needed.

7. Conclusion

This deliverable represents a further development of the management structure and procedures envisioned in the EPOS SP Grant Agreement. The members of the two management boards, namely the Project Council (PC) and Executive Board (EB) have been appointed before the kick-off meeting, held in Brussels on the 10-12 February 2020. Consequently, both the first EB and PC meetings were successfully organized and conducted during the event. The minutes of both meetings have been already circulated corroborating the operational capacity of the ECO.

In addition to the management structure and procedure, this deliverable demonstrates that quality aspects are taken into account in a variety of processes and activities within the project. The interrelated quality processes – planning, assurance and control – impact the project work from its start to its end. The project aims at obtaining a high degree of quality, where outcomes are achieved in terms of the effectiveness and efficiency of working practices, as well as products and standards of project deliverables, reports and outputs in general. This plan seeks to establish the procedures and standards to be employed in the project, and to allocate responsibility for ensuring that these procedures and standards are followed.

The project management team (the Coordinator and ECO) monitors that the above-described processes are fulfilled. In case of any deviations to the planned work the management team is in charge of taking necessary mitigation measures. The plan is effective throughout the lifetime of the project, but is open to revision if necessary. As described in Chapter 3, responsibilities for quality planning, assurance and control are shared between all partners, which allow various views on quality issues in order to reach the optimal outcome.

Annex 1 - Deliverable Template

EPOS Integrating European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth Science

EPOS SP – Grant Agreement n. 871121

Dx.x – Deliverable Title

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EPOS Integrating European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth Science

TABLE OF CONTENTS

SUMMARY 3

1. INTRODUCTION 3

2. 3

3. 3

 3.1 3

 3.2 3

4. 3

5. CONCLUSION 3

6. ANNEX..... 3

Annex 2 - Reporting Templates

Technical Report

EPOS Integrating European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth Science

Project Number: 871121
Project Acronym: EPOS SP
Project title: European Plate Observing System Sustainability Phase

WP1 Periodic Report

No page limit per workpackage but report shall be concise and readable. Any duplication should be avoided.

Work package number	1	Lead beneficiary	1- EPOS ERIC		
Work package title	Project Management				
Participant number	1				
Short name of participant	EPOS ERIC				
Person months per participant	48				

Period covered by the report: from [insert dd/mm/yyyy] to [insert dd/mm/yyyy]
 Periodic report: [1st] [2nd]

Table of content

- 1. Explanation of the work carried per WP 2
 - 1.2 Work carried out during the reporting period 2
- 2. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable) 2
 - 2.1 Tasks 2
 - 2.2 Use of resources 2
 - 2.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting (if applicable) 2
 - 2.2.2 Unforeseen use of in-kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges (if applicable) 3
- 3. Milestones 3
- 4. Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions 3
 - 4.1 Foreseen Risks 3
 - 4.2 Unforeseen Risks 3

EPOS Integrating European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth Science

1. Explanation of the work carried per WP

Include here an overview of the WP project results towards the objective of the action for the reporting period, in line with the structure of the Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement. This overview shall be concise (not more than half page) and readable.

1.2 Work carried out during the reporting period

Task 1.1 Financial & Administrative Management

Task Leader: EPOS ERIC

Explain the work carried out during the reporting period giving details of the work carried out by each beneficiary/linked third party involved

Task 1.2 Project Governance and Internal communication

Task Leader: EPOS ERIC

Explain the work carried out during the reporting period giving details of the work carried out by each beneficiary/linked third party involved

Task 1.3 Risk management and project impact assessment

Task Leader: EPOS ERIC

Explain the work carried out during the reporting period giving details of the work carried out by each beneficiary/linked third party involved/linked third party involved.

2. Deviations from Annex 1 and Annex 2 (if applicable)

Explain the reasons for deviations from the DoA, the consequences and the proposed corrective actions.

2.1 Tasks

Include explanations for tasks not fully implemented, critical objectives not fully achieved and/or not being on schedule. Explain also the impact on other tasks on the available resources and the planning.

2.2 Use of resources

Include explanations on deviations of the use of resources between actual and planned use of resources in Annex 1, especially related to person-months per work package. Include explanations on transfer of costs categories (if applicable). Include explanations on adjustments to previous financial statements (if applicable).

2.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting (if applicable)

Specify in this section:

EPOS Integrating European Research Infrastructures for solid Earth Science

a) the work (the tasks) performed by a subcontractor which may cover only a limited part of the project;

b) explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for a subcontract, taking into account the specific characteristics of the project;

c) the confirmation that the subcontractor has been selected ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price and avoiding any conflict of interests

2.2.2 Unforeseen use of in-kind contribution from third party against payment or free of charges (if applicable)

Specify in this section:

d) the identity of the third party;

e) the resources made available by the third party respectively against payment or free of charges

f) explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for using these resources for carrying out the work.

3. Milestones

Please check and complete the status of the milestones, clicking on the following link:
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1x3N_ZcmYBCmLS4mQ5vSP0z2GkXQawj/edit#gid=1193246264

4. Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions

4.1 Foreseen Risks

4.2 Unforeseen Risks

Please check and complete the status of the risks and mitigation actions, clicking on the following link:
 AVAILABLE SOON

Financial Report

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